

Three-phase Four-wire Bidirectional Y-converter for an Enhanced Interface between the AC Grid and the Unipolar DC Microgrid

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Abstract—In this paper, a modified three-phase four-wire bidirectional topology is proposed for interfacing the DC microgrid with the AC utility grid. The converter comprises three four-switch buck-boost modules in a star connection, while the neutral of the AC-grid is directly connected to the positive rail of the DC side. This converter permits independent control of each of the three modules, allowing it to endure single-phase faults and adjust to unbalanced conditions. Simulation results are presented for various scenarios, including balanced AC-grid voltages in rectification and inversion modes, unbalanced AC-grid voltages with constant input resistance control, constant input current control, and constant input power control. Finally, a 7-kW experimental prototype is developed to verify the converter’s analysis and simulations. The experimental results show that the converter achieved a peak efficiency of 98.87% and maintained an efficiency of 97.66% at its rated output power. Additionally, the converter exhibited resilient operation, showing stability and reliable performance under both balanced and unbalanced conditions.

Index Terms—DC microgrid, Four-wire converters, Y-converter, three-phase modular converters, three-phase rectifiers.

I. INTRODUCTION

The widespread use of renewable energy sources (RES), energy storage systems (ESS), and electric vehicle charging stations is compelling traditional power systems to adapt to handle increased capacities and loads. To integrate distributed energy generation and local demand, DC microgrids (DCMGs) can be employed instead of a conventional utility grid with centralized generation [1].

In order to interconnect the 400 V DC microgrid with the European low voltage grid (with a line-to-line RMS voltage of 400 V), buck-type bidirectional PFC converters are required [2], as presented in Fig. 1. Several topologies with optimized modulation techniques have been proposed in the literature, including the six-switch buck converter with optimized modulation techniques to minimize switching losses and input capacitor voltage distortions [3], the seven-switch buck converter [4], delta-type input current source converter [5], and the Swiss converter [6]. The Y-converter is adopted in [7], [8] as a buck-type bidirectional PFC converter, and it is shown that it potentially has better overall performance compared to

Fig. 1: A bidirectional converter connecting a DC microgrid to an AC grid

the seven-switch and Swiss converters. However, all of the discussed topologies are three-wire topologies, while four-wire topologies for boost-type bidirectional PFC converters are well addressed in the literature, such as the four-leg voltage source converters and the three-level converters [9], [10].

There are many motivations driving the adoption of four-wire topologies in bidirectional PFC converter applications. Since the three phases can be controlled independently in four-wire topologies, fault-tolerant operation and flexibility during unbalanced conditions are achieved. When a phase is disconnected due to a single-phase fault at the AC grid or semiconductor device failure, the remaining two phases can deliver a maximum output power of two-thirds of the rated output power. Moreover, when the AC grid voltages are unbalanced, three different current control modes can be applied to the three phase: equal input resistance, equal input power, and equal AC currents. Finally, the four-wire topology provides both grid-forming capability and the ability to supply single-phase loads connected to the low-voltage AC grid in the event of islanded operation [11].

When considering the adoption of four-wire boost-type topologies to link the 400 V DC microgrid with the European low-voltage grid, it becomes necessary to incorporate an additional buck-stage, as indicated in previous studies [12], [13]. In this two-stage configuration, the converter’s efficiency may suffer due to the double processing of total power with the cascaded connection of converters. Furthermore, the inclusion of an extra DC-link capacitor between the two stages impacts the converter’s physical size and cost [14]. Additionally, when

Fig. 2: A schematic of the four-wire Y-converter

interfacing a 400 V DC microgrid, all semiconductor devices must be rated at the DC-link voltage, which typically exceeds 650 V in the case of four-wire boost-type topologies. Consequently, single-stage topologies, such as the one proposed here, have the potential to enhance overall efficiency while reducing size and cost [15].

In this paper, a modified three-phase four-wire bidirectional step-down converter, displayed in Fig. 2, to enhance the coupling between the AC grid and the unipolar DC microgrid. This topology allows for individual control of the three phases, enabling fault-tolerant operation and increased flexibility, especially in situations with unbalanced AC grid conditions. Furthermore, it possesses the grid-forming capability and enhances its versatility in various operating scenarios. The rest of this paper is structured as follows: The operation principle is explained in Sec. II. Simulation results are presented in Sec. III. Experimental results are presented in Sec. IV. Finally, the conclusion is presented in Sec. V.

II. PRINCIPLE OPERATION

The three-wire Y-converter is formed by joining three buck-boost modules at a central point called m , which is considered the neutral point of the Y-connection of the modules. As each module functions as a DC-DC converter, the voltage on the AC side of the module should remain at a non-negative value. To achieve this, an appropriate offset voltage is needed between the grid neutral point n and m . In sinusoidal pulse width modulation (SPWM), the offset voltage is constant and higher than the peak of the grid AC phase voltage.

In the case of the four-wire Y-converter, the n is connected to the positive rail of the DC side, resulting in a fixed offset voltage equal to the DC side voltage V_{dc} . For proper operation of the four-wire converter when connected to the European distribution grid, V_{dc} must be more than 325 V (the peak value of the phase voltages \hat{V}_m).

The incorporation of the neutral wire into the topology ensures that each module has its own current return path through the neutral wire. This allows for the complete independence of current control within the three modules, thereby enhancing the converter's flexibility when dealing with unbalanced AC grid conditions. Each module's current can be adjusted independently to accommodate AC grid imbalances.

Moreover, in the event of a disconnection of a single module due to a fault in the AC grid or as a result of protective

measures applied to the module, the other two modules are capable of maintaining normal operation and supplying up to two-thirds of the rated power. This significantly enhances the converter's reliability.

For the four-wire topology, v_{am} , v_{bm} , and v_{cm} can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} v_{am} &= \hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t) + V_{dc} \\ v_{bm} &= \hat{V}_m \sin\left(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) + V_{dc} \\ v_{cm} &= \hat{V}_m \sin\left(\omega t + \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) + V_{dc} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

To ensure a clear and simplified analysis, we present a single-module analysis that can be readily extended to the other modules. Focusing on phase a as depicted in Fig. 3a, its module comprises an inductor labeled as L and two half-

(a) Module a of the three-phase modular converter

(b) Buck mode when $v_{am} > V_{dc}$

(c) Boost mode when $v_{am} < V_{dc}$

Fig. 3: Operation modes of one module of the proposed converter include current paths in both buck and boost modes

bridges: one on the AC side (S_{a1}, S_{a2}) and the other on the DC side (S_{a3}, S_{a4}). These two half-bridges are subject to control, such that only one of them is modulated at a given moment, while the other remains clamped based on the values of V_{am} and V_{dc} .

When v_{am} exceeds V_{dc} , module a operates in the buck mode. In this mode, the AC-side half bridge switches, while the DC-side half bridge remains clamped (S_{a3} is activated, and S_{a4} is deactivated), as illustrated in Fig. 3b. To determine the duty cycle of S_{a1} , denoted as $d_{buck,a}$, the following calculation can be applied:

$$d_{buck,a} = \frac{V_{dc}}{v_{am}} = \frac{V_{dc}}{\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t) + V_{dc}} \quad (2)$$

and the duty cycle of S_{a2} is the complementary of $d_{buck,a}$.

Given a sinusoidal mains current with unity power factor, we can derive the average inductor current of module a ($i_{La,av}$) as follows:

$$i_{La,av} = \frac{i_a + i_{Cf,a}}{d_{buck,a}} = \frac{\hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t) + i_{Cf,a}}{d_{buck,a}} \quad (3)$$

Considering i_a as the grid current of phase a , $i_{Cf,a}$ as the current through the input capacitor C_f , and \hat{I}_m as the peak grid current, we can simplify $i_{La,av}$ by neglecting $i_{Cf,a}$ in comparison to I_a as follows:

$$i_{La,av} = \frac{i_a}{d_{buck,a}} = \frac{\hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t)}{d_{buck,a}} \quad (4)$$

Likewise, in the event that v_{am} falls below V_{dc} , module a operates in the boost mode. In this mode, the DC-side half-bridge switches, while the AC-side half bridge remains clamped (S_{a1} is activated, and S_{a2} is deactivated), as depicted in Fig. 3c. To determine the duty cycle of S_{a3} , referred to as $d_{boost,a}$, the following calculation can be applied:

$$d_{boost,a} = \frac{v_{am}}{V_{dc}} = \frac{\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t) + V_{dc}}{V_{dc}} \quad (5)$$

and the duty cycle of S_{a4} is the complementary of $d_{boost,a}$.

Using (4) and given that $d_{buck,a} = 1$ in boost mode, $i_{La,av}$ in boost mode equals:

$$i_{La,av} = i_a = \hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t) \quad (6)$$

The basic characteristic equations for phase a of the four-wire Y-converter are summarized in Table I, where V_a refers to the grid voltage, V_{am} is the AC-side voltage of the module, d_{buck} and d_{boost} are the duty cycles of the upper switch in the AC-side and DC-side half-bridges respectively, and I_{La} and \hat{I}_m are the inductor current and peak grid current respectively. Additionally, the key waveforms are plotted in Fig. 4.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

The performance of the converter is studied and evaluated through simulations and experimental validation under various

TABLE I: Basic equations of the four-wire Y-converter

	$0 \leq t \leq 10ms$	$10ms \leq t \leq 20ms$
V_a	$\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t)$	
V_{am}	$\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t) + V_{dc}$	
d_{buck}	V_{dc}/V_{am}	1
d_{boost}	1	V_{am}/V_{dc}
I_{La}	$\hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t)/d_{buck}$	$\hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t)$

conditions, including balanced AC grid voltages, unbalanced grid voltages, and single-phase/module faults. All tests are conducted at the rated voltages of the AC and DC sides, with a rated power P_r of 7kW. The converter's specifications are summarized in Table 2.

Under balanced grid voltage conditions, the converter waveforms at steady state for both rectification and inversion modes at rated power are displayed in Fig. 5. As is evident from the

Fig. 4: Basic waveforms of the four-wire Y-converter for phase a

TABLE II: Specifications of the four-wire Y-converter

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Rated power	P_r	7 kW
AC line voltage, frequency	V_{ll}, f_o	400 V, 50 Hz
DC voltage	V_{dc}	400 V
Switching frequency	f_{sw}	62.5 kHz
Inductance	L	190 μ H

simulation results, the converter achieves a pure sinusoidal mains current in both modes.

Under unbalanced grid voltage conditions, a performance study is conducted assuming the RMS values of the phase voltages v_a , v_b , and v_c to be 190 V, 230 V, and 210 V, respectively. Three different current control modes are implemented: constant input resistance mode (CR mode), constant input current mode (CI mode), and constant input power mode (CP mode).

In the constant input resistance mode, the converter's modules are regulated to exhibit ohmic behavior, resulting in grid currents that vary in proportion to the grid voltages. The constant input current mode showcases the converter's ability to control the modules to achieve equalized current distribution among the three modules. Finally, in the constant input power mode, the converter's modules are controlled to ensure equalized power distribution among the three modules, effectively minimizing power fluctuations on the DC side. The simulation results under these unbalanced conditions have

Fig. 5: Simulation results for balanced conditions

been visualized in Fig. 6.

The fault-tolerant operation of the proposed converter is validated in the event of a single module disconnection, which may occur due to protective actions or a single feeder disconnection in the AC grid caused by a single-line fault. Thanks to the independent control of each module, the converter can sustain its operation even when one module is disconnected by redistributing power among the remaining modules.

This fault-tolerant operation is demonstrated in Fig. 7. Initially, the converter operates normally with a constant current reference directly fed into the inner current control loop. However, the normal operation is interrupted by the sudden disconnection of module a . Despite this disconnection, the other two modules continue to operate without disruption, allowing the converter to still deliver up to two-thirds of its rated power.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To validate the preceding analysis and simulations, a 7-kW prototype of the four-wire Y-converter has been implemented. The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 8. The prototype incorporated 12 SiC devices with the part number IMZ120R030M1H, rated at 1200 V and 56 A. The converter's main inductors are constructed using sendust powder cores with the part number KoolMu 0079908A7, each wound with 80 turns of litz wires, resulting in a total DC resistance of the inductor of 20.3 m Ω . Additionally, the input AC filter is implemented using a filter inductor L_f with a value of

Fig. 6: Different current control strategies under unbalanced conditions

Fig. 7: fault tolerant operation under one module disconnection

Fig. 8: Experimental setup

50 μH and the part number 7443763540470, along with a filter capacitor C_f with a value of 11.3 μF .

Under balanced AC grid conditions, the main converter waveforms at rated power in rectification and inversion modes are illustrated in Fig. 9a and Fig. 9b, respectively. These captured waveforms encompass the AC grid voltages (v_a , v_b , v_c), AC-side voltage of module a (v_{am}), and the AC grid currents (i_a , i_b , i_c , i_n). Furthermore, the efficiency curve of the prototype is plotted in Fig. 9c, demonstrating a peak efficiency of 98.87% and an efficiency of 97.66% at rated output power.

The transient response under closed-loop control is also evaluated by examining the waveforms of inductor currents and grid currents under step variations. Two specific scenarios are considered: a step change in the output power while in rectification mode and a step change from rectification mode to inversion mode. To assess performance, we analyze the key waveforms of a single module, specifically module a .

In Fig. 10, the converter initially operates in rectification mode at 50% of its rated power. Subsequently, a step change is applied to the grid current references to reach the rated power. The waveforms clearly depict the rapid and stable behavior of both i_a and i_{La} , signifying the efficient and dependable operation of the control structure.

Similarly, Fig. 11 illustrates the step change from recti-

(a) Rectification mode at rated power

(b) Inversion mode at rated power

(c) Efficiency curve of the experimental prototype

Fig. 9: Experimental results under balanced AC grid.

fication mode to inversion mode. The converter undergoes a transition from operating at 50% of its rated power in rectification mode to operating at 50% of its rated power in inversion mode. Once again, the waveforms of i_a and i_{La} exhibit a swift and stable response, underscoring the effectiveness of the control structure.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper introduces a modified three-phase four-wire bidirectional converter designed to interface the DC microgrid with the AC utility grid. The converter configuration involves the interconnection of three four-switch buck-boost modules

Fig. 10: Experimental waveforms under step change of the output power in rectification mode from 50% of rated power to 100% of rated power

Fig. 11: Experimental waveforms under step change from rectification mode to inversion mode

in a star configuration, with the AC grid's neutral linked to the positive rail of the DC microgrid. The incorporation of the neutral wire into the topology allows for the complete independence of current control within the three modules. This independent control of these three modules is demonstrated by the implementation of three distinct current control modes during unbalanced conditions: the constant input resistance mode, simulating an ohmic behavior for each module; the constant input current mode, evenly distributing the current among the modules; and the constant input power mode, which minimizes power fluctuations on the DC microgrid side. Additionally, the proposed converter exhibits both fault-tolerant capability in the event of single-phase faults and grid-forming capability. The paper validates the converter's performance through simulations and experimental results, including the construction and testing of a practical prototype rated at 7 kW. The experimental outcomes affirm the converter's exceptional efficiency, achieving a peak efficiency of 98.87% and maintaining an efficiency of 97.66% at the rated output power.

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